

Improving the Quality of Wind Field Reconstruction

Techniques for Lidar-assisted Control of Wind Turbines

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Outline

- **Problem setting**
- **Methods**
- **Results**
- **Outlook**

Lidar systems' temporal and spatial limitations

By concept: *uses the Doppler effect, thus measures **LINE-OF-SIGHT** wind speed*

By design: *discrete measurements in **SPACE** and **TIME***

- Take advantage of the trade-offs of lidar technology to use its potential and specifically to apply it to the control of wind energy conversion systems.

Problem setting

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Objective: *Develop a closure model for the wind field dynamics that can be used to approximate the unavailable data based on the available ones.*

Methods

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Results

Results obtained using Kaimal (1972) turbulence model (TurbSim, IEC 61400-1) : two-point measurement scheme (left), four-point measurement scheme (right)

Results

Results obtained using Kaimal (1972) turbulence model (TurbSim, IEC 61400-1) and Kaimal model based analytical model: two-point measurement scheme (left), four-point measurement scheme (right)*

* David Schlipf. "Lidar-Assisted Control Concepts for Wind Turbines". PhD thesis. University of Stuttgart, 2015. DOI: 10.18419/opus-8796.

Results

*Results obtained using open-source LES wind field data (four-point measurement scheme)**

* Open-source EllipSys3D data: <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-2019-65>

Outlook

What should a simplified LES wind model look like?

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- ***Capable of running in real time***
- ***Act as a one-time-step predictor***
- ***3D extendable***

ABL Incompressible Navier–Stokes Equations

$$\frac{u}{r} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \psi} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{v}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \psi} + w \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} - \frac{v^2}{r} \right] = 2\Omega v - \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + v \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \psi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} - \frac{u}{r^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \psi} \right)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial v}{\partial r} + \frac{v}{r} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \psi} + w \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + \frac{uv}{r} \right] = 2\Omega u - \frac{1}{\rho_0 r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \psi} + v \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial \psi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} - \frac{v}{r^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \psi} \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} + \frac{v}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial \psi} + w \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = g \left(\frac{\theta - \theta_0}{\theta_0} \right) - \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + v \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \psi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial z^2} \right)$$

- No viscous diffusion
- No effects of pressure gradient (thermodynamics)
- No Coriolis forcing terms
- No effect due to the vertical component

Unsteady acceleration + Convective acceleration + Nonlinear term

Consistent with Taylor's frozen turbulence hypothesis

* Stull RB. An Introduction to Boundary Layer Meteorology, Vol. 13. Springer: New York City, 1988.

** P Towers and B LI Jones. "Real-time wind field reconstruction from LiDAR measurements using a dynamic wind model and state estimation". In: Wind Energy 19.1 (2016), pp. 133–150

Outlook

An extension of the framework will include full aero-elastic simulations to evaluate the methods for their capability in improving wind turbine control.

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Thanks for attention!